

panicles were produced with both CO₂ enrichment and increasing N treatment (see table). Similar trends in individual seed mass were observed while filled grains/panicle were apparently unaffected by either CO₂ or N treatment. These trends in grain yield and final aboveground biomass resulted in a decline in harvest index with increasing N treatment (especially in the 660 μmol/mol). Harvest index tended to be higher in the CO₂ enrichment treatments.

Canopy gross photosynthesis and canopy light utilization efficiency were increased by both CO₂ enrichment and increasing N fertilizer throughout the growing season. Canopy dark respiration rate expressed on a ground area basis followed seasonal trends that were similar to those observed for canopy photosynthesis. Canopy dark respiration rates expressed on a plant dry weight basis declined exponentially throughout the growing season and were little affected by either CO₂ or N fertilizer treatments. After complete canopy closure, CO₂ enrichment reduced canopy evapotranspiration and increased canopy photosynthetic water use efficiency.

The effects of CO₂ enrichment at N levels of 100 and 200 kg/ha on growth, grain yield, and canopy gas exchange are similar to our previous CO₂ enrichment studies (Baker et al 1990, 1992a, b). The relatively small plant responses to N fertilizer treatments are attributed to the high native fertility and organic matter content of the soil used in this experiment.

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Grain yield, components of yield, total above-ground biomass, and harvest index for rice grown in controlled environments chambers.

CO ₂ (μmol/mol)	Nitrogen (kg/ha)	Grain yield (mg/ha)	Panicles (no./plant)	Filled grains (no./panicle)	Individual grain mass (mg/seed)	Aboveground biomass (g/plant)	Harvest Index (g/g)
330	0	6.0	2.8	48.2	18.7	5.5	0.47
	100	8.2	3.3	53.4	20.3	7.3	0.48
	200	8.1	4.0	47.4	18.5	8.1	0.43
660	0	7.9	3.4	49.2	20.6	6.4	0.54
	100	7.9	3.7	49.4	19.6	7.2	0.49
	200	10.1	4.4	53.4	19.2	9.3	0.47
SE ^a		1.46	0.39	7.56	0.97	1.02	0.044
		<i>F value^b</i>					
CO ₂		7.5**	15.4**	0.2 ns	4.1*	4.8*	8.9**
N		8.0**	26.7**	0.5 ns	5.0**	27.1**	6.5**
CO ₂ × N		3.1*	0.5 ns	1.6 ns	6.5**	1.6 ns	16 ns

^aSE in each column is for each of the means and was obtained by pooling each of the within-chamber variances. ^b*, ** = significant at the 0.05 and 0.01 probability levels, respectively. ns = not significant.

Effects of carbon dioxide on competition between rice and barnyard grass

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Effects of elevated CO₂ on rice production could occur not only through direct impacts on rice (Baker et al 1990) but also indirectly via ecosystem responses (Bazzaz et al 1985). Preliminary experiments were conducted to test the hypothesis that a C3 crop, rice, and a C4 weed, barnyard grass, respond differently to CO₂, affecting competition between them when grown at different relative densities in the same container.

Rice cultivar IR72 and barnyard grass were grown from seeds obtained from IRRI. Four-day-old seedlings were transplanted into white plastic pots (7.5 cm high × 16.5 cm inner diameter) filled with soil. Plants were arranged in a circle in each pot, with one in the center for the one-plant pots. Plants were watered periodically to maintain standing water with nutrient solution.

Carbon dioxide treatments were provided in individual small-exposure chambers located in a greenhouse with rough temperature and light intensity control but no dewpoint control. Average conditions over two experiments were photosynthetically active radiation (PAR), average daily at 388 μmol/m² per

s; 12 h light period; temperature, average daily maximum of 25.4 °C, average daily minimum of 26.3 °C; and relative humidity, average day period minimum of 42%, average night period maximum, 69%.

Carbon dioxide treatments were ambient (average 374 μL/L), and ambient + continuously added CO₂, resulting in elevated levels of 563, 724, and 895 μL/L. Each CO₂ level occurred in each of two blocks of chambers. Plants were exposed to CO₂ for about 28 d. Seven planting mixtures/densities were examined per chamber (split/plots): 8 barnyard grass, 2 rice and 6 barnyard grass, 4 rice and 4 barnyard grass, 6 rice and 2 barnyard grass, 8 rice, 1 rice, and 1 barnyard grass, with two replicate pots per density per chamber. The experiment was repeated. Both experiments were evaluated together because no significant (at P < 0.05) experiment × CO₂ interactions and few experiment × density interactions were found. Rice and barnyard grass data were analyzed separately (per plant).

Rice plants tended to have increased shoot growth under elevated CO₂ levels. Across densities, elevated CO₂ produced a statistically significant increase in rice leaf number (P < 0.05) (see table), but increases for tiller number and leaf, stem, and total dry weight (Fig. 1) were significant only with P = 0.05-0.16. Few lower P values may be because of, in part, a lack of difference in response among higher CO₂ levels. Density across CO₂ levels had a highly significant effect on all param-

Results from statistical analysis (P values) of effects of experiment, CO₂, and density on rice and barnyard grass (BYG). The density comparisons are for 1 vs 8 plants/pot (only intraspecific competition) and 1 vs all multiple plants (2-8)/pot (includes interspecific competition).

Source	df	Tiller no.		Leaf no.		Leaf dry weight		Stem dry weight		Total dry weight	
		Rice	BYG	Rice	BYG	Rice	BYG	Rice	BYG	Rice	BYG
Experiment	1	0.14	0.04	0.36	0.03	0.02	0.04	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.01
Block	2	0.07	0.79	0.10	0.43	0.05	0.47	0.08	0.07	0.12	0.05
CO ₂	3	0.05	0.42	0.04	0.48	0.12	0.29	0.08	0.18	0.16	0.01
Experiment × CO ₂	3	0.33	0.52	0.27	0.11	0.12	0.25	0.19	0.56	0.16	0.92
Density	4	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.11	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
(1 vs 8 plants)	1	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.03	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
(1 vs 2-8 plants)	1	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.02	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
Experiment × density	4	0.08	0.34	0.36	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.03	0.07	0.01	0.22
CO ₂ × density	12	<0.01	0.43	<0.01	0.88	<0.01	0.50	0.07	0.66	0.06	0.62
Chamber (Experiment × CO ₂)	7	0.09	0.38	0.28	0.85	0.40	0.48	0.11	0.24	0.07	0.52
Error	124	(123 for leaf dry weight)									
Total	159	(158 for leaf dry weight)									

eters ($P < 0.01$), largely because of the increase in growth at 1 plant/pot vs other densities.

Rice plants showed significant ($P < 0.05$) CO₂ × density interactions for leaf and tiller numbers and marginally significant interactions ($P = 0.06-0.07$) for stem and total shoot dry weight (see table). In terms of interspecific competition, rice tended to compete better with barnyard grass under elevated CO₂ levels compared with ambient CO₂; the mixtures with more rice and fewer barnyard grass plants per pot showed greater increases in growth (Fig. 1a). In terms of intraspecific competition, CO₂ stimulated rice plant growth more with one rice plant/pot compared with 8 plants/pot for all parameters.

As expected for C4 plants, barnyard grass showed no significant increase in

shoot growth with elevated CO₂, either with or without plant competition (see table), and there actually was a significant decrease in total dry weight primarily at low densities (Fig. 1b). Density by itself—across CO₂ levels—significantly affected all parameters except leaf dry weight ($P < 0.01$), with less growth when more plants were present in a pot.

Barnyard grass shoot growth did not show any significant (lowest $P = 0.43$) CO₂ × density interactions (see table), likely because of the lack of a general CO₂ response for this species. In terms of general competition, (across all CO₂ concentrations), barnyard grass growth tended to be less with more barnyard grass compared with rice plants in the mixtures. This (coupled with greater growth with 1 vs. 8 barnyard grass plants/pot) suggested

Effects of CO₂ and plant density on total shoot dry weight of a) rice and b) barnyard grass. Data are per plant and averages of eight plants, two from each of two experiments. Coefficients of variability across CO₂ levels, densities, and experiments were 44.7% for rice and 26.0% for barnyard grass.

that intraspecific competition among barnyard grass plants was more important than interspecific competition with rice. With increasing CO₂ concentrations, however, there was a trend toward decreased barnyard grass growth in the mixtures, suggesting that rice plants were becoming more competitive.

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A very simple model of crop growth: derivation and application

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Crop growth models are powerful tools to improve understanding of global climate change and to predict crop yield changes caused by these changes. The problem, however, is that models are often so complex that it is difficult to understand them. We have a very simple model (VSM) for determining crop growth. The